

Understanding the Fundamentals of Artificial Light Exposure on Animals and Humans

Chayan Munshi¹

DOI:

Abstract: Increase of human-initiated activities have impacted our ecosystem along with the residing animals and humans. Anthropogenic activities in today's world have significantly impacted the ecosystem and the biodiversity, which is undoubtedly an issue of concern for contemporary researchers. Urbanization is the major cause of anthropogenic infestation in the wildlife, where artificial light at night (ALAN) plays a critical role in affecting the day-night cycle. Assessment the behavioural plasticity in response to environmental trepidation by ALAN includes several disciplines and high-end protocols, thus making this area of concern for researchers from diverse expertise. Long-term studies would help to understand the adaptability of animals and humans in the altering ecosystems. Through this abstract, I will discuss the consideration of several behavioural markers in different animals to correlate with the ALAN-induced neuroethological stress in those animals. It is also focused to elucidate, how some aspects light pollution due to man-made smart devices and its related impact of over digitalization which creates "brain rot" and eventually challenge the fundamental behavioural response in humans. It is essentially critical at this stage to understand the evolutionary responses of humans and animal to the unnatural like ALAN.

Keywords: light exposure, behavioural plasticity, evolutionary ecology.

Corresponding Author: chayan.munshi@ethophilia.com

¹Ethophilia Research Foundation, Santiniketan, India